

Studies on thermodynamic and transport properties of binary solutions of *m*-xylene and 1-alkanols at 303.15 K

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Abstract : The densities, ρ , viscosities, η , and refractive indices, n_D of binary liquid mixtures of *m*-xylene with 1-alkanols (methanol, ethanol, propan-1-ol, butan-1-ol, pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol, nonan-1-ol and decan-1-ol) have been measured at 303.15 K, as a function of mole fraction by using a vibrating-tube digital densimeter, a Ubbelohde type capillary viscometer and a digital refractometer, respectively. These data have been used to estimate the excess molar volumes, V_m^E , deviation in viscosity, $\Delta\eta$, deviation in refractive index, Δn_D , deviation in molar refraction, $\Delta_x R$, excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow, G^E and Grunberg and Nissan parameter, d over the whole range of composition. These parameters have been interpreted in terms of the nature of heteromolecular interactions occurring in these systems. The effect of size of alkyl chain length of 1-alkanols has been studied.

Keywords : Excess molar volumes, viscosities, *m*-xylene, 1-alkanols, refractive indices.

Introduction

Thermodynamic and transport properties data of multicomponent liquid systems are needed in many industrial applications¹⁻⁵. In continuation of our previous work⁶ and to extend the thermodynamic and transport properties studies for a series of alcohols, now we report the densities, ρ , viscosities, η , and refractive indices, n_D for the following binary mixtures : *m*-xylene + methanol (MeOH), + ethanol (EtOH), + propan-1-ol (PrOH), butan-1-ol (BuOH), + pentan-1-ol (PeOH), + hexan-1-ol (HeOH), + heptan-1-ol (HpOH), + octan-1-ol (OcOH), + nonan-1-ol (NnOH) and decan-1-ol (DeOH) at 303.15 K. The excess molar volume, V_m^E , deviations in viscosity, $\Delta\eta$, refractive index, Δn_D , and molar refraction, $\Delta_x R$, excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow, G^E and Grunberg and Nissan parameter, d have been estimated from the measured experimental data over the whole composition range.

Results and discussion

Densities, ρ for the binary mixtures of *m*-xylene and 1-alkanols [(C₁-C₂) and (C₆-C₁₀)], whereas viscosities, η and refractive indices, n_D for binary mixtures of *m*-xylene and 1-alkanols (C₁-C₁₀) were measured over the whole mole fraction range at 303.15 K. *m*-Xylene is indicated

as component 1 and 1-alkanols as component 2. Density data were used to determine the molar volumes, V_m and excess molar volumes, V_m^E by using following equations :

$$V_m = (x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2) / \rho \quad (1)$$

$$V_m^E = x_1 M_1 (1/\rho - 1/\rho_1) + x_2 M_2 (1/\rho - 1/\rho_2) \quad (2)$$

where x_1 , x_2 and M_1 , M_2 are the mole fractions and molar masses, and ρ_1 and ρ_2 are densities of the pure components 1 and 2 respectively, ρ is the density of the binary mixture.

The viscosity data were used to determine deviation in viscosities, $\Delta\eta$ from ideality by using the equation :

$$\Delta\eta = \eta - (x_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \eta_2) \quad (3)$$

where η_1 , η_2 are the viscosities of pure components 1 and 2 respectively. η is the viscosity of the binary mixture. Similarly deviation in refractive index, Δn_D and deviation in molar refraction, $\Delta_x R$ have been determined by using the equations :

$$\Delta n_D = n_D - (x_1 n_{D,1} + x_2 n_{D,2}) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta_x R = R - x_1 R_1 - x_2 R_2 \quad (5)$$

where $n_{D,1}$, $n_{D,2}$ and R_1 , R_2 are the refractive indices and molar refractions of pure components, n_D and R are the refractive index and molar refraction of binary mixture, respectively.

Table-1 (contd.)

0.2000	0.83843	2.5842	1.4321	35.3337	-73.56	-0.658
0.3002	0.84683	1.8945	1.4383	35.1083	-138.22	-0.988
0.4000	0.85298	1.3944	1.4450	35.0052	-199.40	-1.278
0.5004	0.85731	1.1374	1.4520	34.9856	-196.65	-1.208
0.6000	0.85945	0.9537	1.4598	35.0996	-176.82	-1.130
0.6998	0.86094	0.7466	1.4673	35.2073	-197.65	-1.469
0.7997	0.86036	0.6244	1.4755	35.4325	-177.18	-1.747
0.9001	0.85932	0.5326	1.4838	35.6687	-143.92	-2.560
1.0000	0.85553	0.5448	1.4919	35.9972	-	-
<i>m</i> -Xylene + OcOH						
0.0000	0.82129	6.1350	1.4256	40.5956	-	-
0.1000	0.83618	4.5756	1.4302	39.5053	-38.10	-0.568
0.1500	0.84052	3.6192	1.4331	39.1603	-107.87	-1.291
0.2500	0.84928	2.7183	1.4381	38.4019	-137.44	-1.113
0.4000	0.85933	1.7404	1.4475	37.5356	-189.98	-1.214
0.5000	0.86480	1.3647	1.4537	36.9920	-191.80	-1.170
0.6000	0.86650	1.0685	1.4608	36.6558	-192.12	-1.229
0.7000	0.86635	0.8354	1.4680	36.3824	-192.31	-1.423
0.8000	0.86345	0.6458	1.4761	36.2596	-197.66	-1.964
0.9000	0.85973	0.5600	1.4838	36.1188	-133.49	-2.385
1.0000	0.85553	0.5448	1.4919	35.9972	-	-
<i>m</i> -Xylene + NnOH						
0.0000	0.82284	7.9200	1.4295	45.2435	-	-
0.1000	0.83779	5.5504	1.4342	43.6755	-59.08	-0.976
0.2000	0.84663	4.2732	1.4385	42.4097	-57.43	-0.510
0.3176	0.85544	2.9530	1.4447	41.0951	-92.25	-0.629
0.4300	0.86382	2.0093	1.4508	39.8457	-145.24	-0.900
0.5200	0.86891	1.5540	1.4563	38.9566	-156.11	-0.948
0.6995	0.86947	1.0002	1.4685	37.6381	-129.16	-0.936
0.7900	0.86830	0.8812	1.4752	37.0324	-57.80	-0.490
0.8975	0.86260	0.5856	1.4835	36.4760	-126.29	-2.197
1.0000	0.85553	0.5448	1.4919	35.9972	-	-
<i>m</i> -Xylene + DeOH						
0.0000	0.82313	9.8110	1.4336	50.0360	-	-
0.1004	0.84005	6.6837	1.4366	47.6932	-62.38	-1.036
0.3060	0.85762	3.8931	1.4448	44.1541	-31.88	-0.187
0.4000	0.86460	2.8033	1.4494	42.6691	-67.21	-0.401
0.5136	0.87286	1.7539	1.4553	40.9036	-154.13	-0.948
0.6010	0.87359	1.2965	1.4612	39.8947	-182.63	-1.195
0.7014	0.87309	0.8904	1.4685	38.7931	-232.65	-1.776
0.8998	0.86405	0.6015	1.4830	36.8181	-118.31	-2.115
1.0000	0.85553	0.5448	1.4919	35.9972	-	-

^aMole fraction of *m*-xylene.

$$A^E = x_1 x_2 \sum_{j=1}^n A_{j-1} (x_1 - x_2)^{(j-1)} \quad (8)$$

where A^E , A_j and n are the excess property, polynomial coefficient and polynomial degree, respectively. The values of coefficients of eq. (8) for various excess properties and standard deviation, σ are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The values of the coefficients of eq. (8) and standard deviation σ for the *m*-xylene + 1-alkanols mixtures at 303.15 K

	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	σ
<i>m</i> -Xylene + MeOH					
V_m^E	0.2443	0.1175	-0.0150	0.3841	0.0093
$\Delta\eta$	-0.2171	-0.1137	-0.8236	0.1987	0.0128
Δn_D	0.1951	-0.0086	-0.0045	-0.0936	0.0019
$\Delta_x R$	1.5826	3.1265	-0.9662	-3.2122	0.0739
G^E	98.92	-263.88	-945.99	236.91	15.582
<i>m</i> -Xylene + EtOH					
V_m^E	0.1829	-0.0950	-0.1227	0.8195	0.0073
$\Delta\eta$	-0.8387	0.2618	-1.1359	0.4252	0.0180
Δn_D	0.1256	-0.0312	-0.0217	-0.0102	0.0010
$\Delta_x R$	1.7306	0.3733	-1.5905	-0.3398	0.0410
G^E	-545.18	-55.81	-59.10	1775.42	25.871
<i>m</i> -Xylene + PrOH					
$\Delta\eta$	-1.728	0.5721	-1.0331	0.8108	0.0086
Δn_D	0.0960	-0.0172	-0.0442	0.0021	0.0009
$\Delta_x R$	1.5574	-5.2360	11.4879	-4.2521	1.0494
G^E	-902.2	101.8	130.0	-1017.7	25.686
<i>m</i> -Xylene + BuOH					
$\Delta\eta$	-2.6165	1.0845	-1.9634	1.5746	0.0309
Δn_D	0.0331	0.0058	-0.0255	-0.0090	0.0006
$\Delta_x R$	-0.7976	0.5789	0.1755	-1.6491	0.0317
G^E	-963.38	-22.27	-701.31	-116.40	15.240
<i>m</i> -Xylene + PeOH					
$\Delta\eta$	-3.0668	1.3783	3.9778	-3.4810	0.0474
Δn_D	-0.0057	0.0008	0.0030	0.0011	0.0001
$\Delta_x R$	-2.8123	0.4965	-0.2699	-2.2821	0.0207
G^E	-944.83	-101.04	-591.64	-133.60	13.262
<i>m</i> -Xylene + HeOH					
V_m^E	-10.556	3.209	1.237	-6.410	0.0835
$\Delta\eta$	-4.1383	1.1185	3.1490	-3.4682	0.0151
Δn_D	-0.0115	-0.0008	0.0037	0.0154	0.0005
$\Delta_x R$	-3.3552	0.6352	0.4981	-0.7371	0.0538
G^E	-894.86	-249.15	-358.14	-284.55	22.509

All the excess properties were fitted by the method of least squares to the following Redlich-Kister type equation :

Table-2 (contd.)

<i>m</i> -Xylene + HpOH					
V_m^E	-14.092	3.162	-0.269	-1.858	0.0261
$\Delta\eta$	-5.2533	2.5515	-0.5495	-1.4901	0.0491
Δn_D	-0.0162	0.0029	0.0043	0.0007	0.0001
$\Delta_x R$	-4.1175	0.9384	0.1493	-0.6226	0.0167
G^E	-773.04	-126.28	-173.14	-877.35	18.956
<i>m</i> -Xylene + OcOH					
V_m^E	-18.254	0.851	0.753	10.733	0.0871
$\Delta\eta$	-7.9550	5.0778	-2.7269	-2.6123	0.0884
Δn_D	-0.0200	0.0013	0.0044	0.0067	0.0002
$\Delta_x R$	-5.0989	0.2123	0.4800	3.2966	0.0325
G^E	-764.5	22.8	-622.5	-1168.2	13.637
<i>m</i> -Xylene + NnOH					
V_m^E	-21.147	-0.482	-1.759	9.456	0.1825
$\Delta\eta$	-10.172	4.642	-2.341	2.485	0.1204
Δn_D	-0.0226	0.0006	0.0043	-0.0040	0.0002
$\Delta_x R$	-5.7296	-0.1168	-0.1567	2.1635	0.0478
G^E	-539.21	19.19	-102.03	-557.06	42.898
<i>m</i> -Xylene + DeOH					
V_m^E	-25.097	-0.057	-4.434	13.605	0.2600
$\Delta\eta$	-12.757	2.425	-5.561	10.491	0.1336
Δn_D	-0.0313	0.0031	0.0005	-0.0064	0.0004
$\Delta_x R$	-7.2298	0.4239	-1.1280	3.1649	0.0963
G^E	-519.8	1400.2	-720.4	1564.8	12.269

The plots of excess molar volumes, V_m^E versus mole fraction, x_1 of *m*-xylene for binary mixtures (Fig. 1), show small positive V_m^E values for *m*-xylene + MeOH and EtOH systems, and large negative V_m^E values for systems containing (C₆-C₁₀) 1-alkanols (minima lie at/near $x_1 \approx 0.5$). Further the negative contributions increase with increase in carbon chain length of 1-alkanols. V_m^E values for (C₃-C₅) 1-alkanols have also been included in

Fig. 1. Excess molar volume, V_m^E vs X_1 for *m*-xylene (1) + 1-alkanols (2) at 303.15 K : $\diamond$, *m*-xylene + MeOH; $\square$, + EtOH; Δ , + PrOH; $\times$, + BuOH; $\blacksquare$, + PeOH; $*$, + HeOH; $+$, + HpOH; $-$, + OcOH; $-$, + NnOH; $\blacklozenge$, + DeOH.

Fig. 1 from reference (8) for comparison. Prabhavathi *et al.* have reported⁸ both positive and negative V_m^E values at 303.15 K for *m*-xylene + propan-1-ol, butan-1-ol and pentan-1-ol systems at higher and lower mole fractions of *m*-xylene respectively.

The viscosities of binary mixtures are positive (Fig. 2), which decrease with increase in concentration of *m*-xylene, except in the case of MeOH. The values of

Fig. 2. Viscosity, η vs X_1 for *m*-xylene (1) + 1-alkanols (2) at 303.15 K : $\diamond$, *m*-xylene + MeOH; $\square$, + EtOH; Δ , + PrOH; $\times$, + BuOH; $\blacksquare$, + PeOH; $*$, + HeOH; $+$, + HpOH; $-$, + OcOH; $-$, + NnOH; $\blacklozenge$, + DeOH.

η for 1-alkanols (except MeOH) are higher than that of *m*-xylene and increase in the following order : MeOH < EtOH < PrOH < BuOH < ... DeOH. The values of $\Delta\eta$ are negative (Fig. 3) for all the systems and their magnitudes increase with increase in carbon chain length

Fig. 3. Deviation in viscosity, $\Delta\eta$ vs X_1 for *m*-xylene (1) + 1-alkanols (2) at 303.15 K : $\diamond$, *m*-xylene + MeOH; $\square$, + EtOH; Δ , + PrOH; $\times$, + BuOH; $\blacksquare$, + PeOH; $*$, + HeOH; $+$, + HpOH; $-$, + OcOH; $-$, + NnOH; $\blacklozenge$, + DeOH.

in 1-alkanols over the whole composition range. The minima lie between 0.4 and 0.5 mole fractions of *m*-xylene i.e. in the alcohol rich region for solutions containing lower 1-alkanols and the curves are slightly shifted toward the *m*-xylene rich region in case of higher 1-alkanols.

The refractive indices increase with increase in mole fraction of *m*-xylene in all the systems (Table 1). The Δn_D values (Fig. 4) are positive for *m*-xylene + (C₁-C₄) 1-alkanol binary mixtures and their magnitudes decrease from MeOH to BuOH. The negative values of Δn_D have been observed for rest of the systems whose magnitudes increase from C₅ to C₁₀ 1-alkanols.

Fig. 4. Deviation in refractive index, Δn_D vs X_1 for *m*-xylene (1) + 1-alkanols (2) at 303.15 K : $\diamond$, *m*-xylene + MeOH; $\square$, + EtOH; Δ , + PrOH; $\times$, + BuOH; $\blacksquare$, + PeOH; $*$, + HeOH; $+$, + HpOH; $-$, + OcOH; $-$, + NnOH; $\blacklozenge$, + DeOH.

The plots of $\Delta_x R$ versus x_1 (Fig. 5) show positive and negative values for $\Delta_x R$ from (C₁-C₃) and (C₄-C₁₀) 1-alkanols, respectively. The V_m^E values result from the

Fig. 5. Deviation in molar refraction, $\Delta_x R$ vs X_1 for *m*-xylene (1) + 1-alkanols (2) at 303.15 K : $\diamond$, *m*-xylene + MeOH; $\square$, + EtOH; Δ , + PrOH; $\times$, + BuOH; $\blacksquare$, + PeOH; $*$, + HeOH; $+$, + HpOH; $-$, + OcOH; $-$, + NnOH; $\blacklozenge$, + DeOH.

various opposing effects. The positive V_m^E values arise due to the breaking of hydrogen bonds in self associated 1-alkanols and physical dipole-dipole interactions between 1-alkanol monomers and multimers. Negative contributions arise from changes of 'free volume' in the real mixture and presence of π -electrons in *m*-xylene molecule resulting in the formation of weak intermolecular com-

plexes⁸. A large decrease in V_m^E values observed in present systems containing long-chain 1-alkanols suggests the formation of OH... π electron hydrogen-bonded complexes. The large decrease in $\Delta\eta$, $\Delta_x R$ and Δn_D (Figs. 3-5) also becomes more in case of higher alcohols which is similar to V_m^E results. Similarly from volumetric, viscometric and refractometric studied for *N,N'*-DMF and 1-alkanols (C₁-C₁₀), we reported⁶ that strong molecular interactions predominate in mixtures containing long-chain 1-alkanols, while weaker/repulsive interactions predominate in the case of short-chain 1-alkanols. Prabhavathi *et al.*⁸ from V_m^E and ΔK_S results for *m*-xylene + propan-1-ol, + butan-1-ol and pentan-1-ol have also concluded that weak interactions exist between component molecules. Negative V_m^E values for (C₃-C₅) 1-alkanols observed in the present work at all mole fractions of *m*-xylene indicate the presence of weak intermolecular interactions.

Gibbs free energy of activation of flow, G^E and Grunberg and Nissan parameter, d have also been calculated (Table 1) and overall these parameters are found to be negative. As the mixtures with strong interactions between the molecules of the components show positive values for Gibbs free energy for activation of flow and the Grunberg and Nissan parameters. Therefore, the negative values of G^E and d obtained strengthens the earlier arguments that weak molecular interactions exist between the components, whose magnitude increase with chain length of 1-alkanols.

Experimental

Methanol, ethanol (Qualigens, A.R.), *m*-xylene, propan-1-ol, pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol (SD Fine Chem. Ltd., A.R.), butan-1-ol (Ranbaxy Labs. Ltd., A.R.), nonan-1-ol (Lancaster), octan-1-ol and decan-1-ol (Spectro Chem. Pvt. Ltd., A.R.) were used without further purification. All the solutions were prepared by mass ratios with a Sartorius balance accurate to 0.01 mg and stored in the air-tight stoppered measuring flasks. The possible error in the mole fraction is estimated to be less than 1×10^{-4} .

A vibrating-tube digital densimeter (Model DMA 60/602 Anton Paar, Austria) was used to measure the densities of the pure liquids and mixtures. An efficient constant temperature bath (Heto Birkerod/Denmark) having a stability within ± 0.01 K, was used to control the temperature of the water flowing around the densimeter cell. The details of the functioning of the densimeter have been discussed elsewhere⁶.

The viscosities of the solutions were determined by using Ubbelohde-type capillary viscometer calibrated by measuring the efflux time of distilled water from 298.15 to 318.15 K. The efflux time was measured with an electronic stop watch with a time resolution of ± 0.01 s, and the average of at least four readings was taken. The thermal stability of the temperature bath was within ± 0.01 K. The viscosities η of solutions were calculated by using the following expression :

$$\eta/\rho = at - b/t \quad (9)$$

where a and b are the viscometer constants. The reproducibility of the measured viscosities was better than ± 0.001 mPa.s.

A digital refractometer (RX-1000, Atago Co. Ltd.) was used to measure refractive indices with an error less than ± 0.0001 . The calibration was carried out with the distilled water. The temperature was maintained constant (within 0.01 K) by circulating water through the prism of refractometer using the constant temperature bath.

Conclusion :

Excess molar volumes, deviations in viscosity, refractive index and molar refraction have been determined for binary mixtures of *m*-xylene + (C₁-C₁₀) 1-alkanols over the whole composition range from density, viscosity and refractive index measurements carried out at 303.15 K. It has been concluded that weak intermolecular interactions exist through possible hydrogen bond formation of the type OH... π electron between 1-alkanol and *m*-xylene

molecules. Further the strength of interactions increase with increase in size of alkyl chain length of 1-alkanols.

References

1. A. Pineiro, P. Brocos, A. Amigo, M. Pintos and R. Bravo, *J. Solution Chem.*, 2002, **31**, 369.
2. P. Brocos, A. Pineiro, R. Bravo and A. Amigo, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2003, **5**, 550.
3. M. Born and E. Wolf, "Principles of Optics", 6th ed., Pergamon, Oxford, 1983, p. 84
4. J. M. Prausnitz, R. N. Lichtenthaler and E. Gomes de Azevedo, "Molecular Thermodynamics of Fluid-Phase Equilibria", 3rd ed., Prentice-Hall, New Jersey, 1999, p. 68.
5. J. O. Hirschfelder, C. F. Curtiss and R. B. Bird, "Molecular Theory of Gases and Liquids", Wiley, London, 1964, Chap. 12.
6. P. K. Banipal, J. Arora, M. Singh and T. S. Banipal, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India, Sect. A*, 2008, **78**.
7. L. Grunberg and A. H. Nissan, *Nature*, 1949, **164**, 799.
8. C. L. Prabhavathi, K. Sivakumar, P. Venkateswarlu and G. K. Raman, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 294.
9. "Thermodynamic Tables of Non-Hydrocarbons", Thermodynamic Research Center, Texas A and M University, College Station, TX, 1994.
10. J. A. Riddick and E. E. Toops, "Organic Solvents : Physical Properties and Methods of Purification", Interscience Publishers, Inc., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1967. Vol. VII, Chap. III.
11. H. Iloukhani and Z. Rostami, *J. Solution Chem.*, 2003, **32**, 451.
12. J. Chao, R. C. Wilhott and B. J. Zwolinski, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data*, 1993, **2**, 427.